

INFORMATION DOCUMENT FOR HOUSEHOLD OWNERS

STUDY TITLE:

1. The epidemiology of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* at a household level in Malawi

INTRODUCTION

This project will investigate the transmission routes of bacteria around a household, with the long-term aim to reduce the spread of disease in Malawi. In order to do this we are asking for your permission to take stool samples from the human members of your household (both children and adults), animals owned and looked after by members of the household, wild animals and birds and samples from the environment around the household. We are also planning to investigate the presence of animal parasites in Chikwawa and Blantyre using the stool samples collected from animals, and the exposure of animals, particularly livestock (cattle, sheep and goats) to diseases which can affect both humans and animals, by examination of a small blood sample taken from animals.

Dr Catherine Wilson, undertaking the project, is a veterinary surgeon based at the University of Liverpool, and this project makes up her PhD project. She is working in collaboration with the Liverpool-Malawi Wellcome Trust laboratories, Blantyre, and the International Livestock Research Institute, Kenya.

WHAT IS THIS RESEARCH FOR?

The stool samples are being taken to look for the presence of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella*. The project will study the connections between the *E. coli* detected in human and animal members of the same household. Non-typhoidal *Salmonella* causes a high rate of death and serious illness in humans, particularly amongst children and the elderly. Faecal contamination of the environment by humans or animals carrying the bacteria, can also be another way to spread disease throughout a household. Currently the exact route of disease transmission of the bacteria is unknown.

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Samples taken from human and animal household members, as well as the environment, will be used to try to detect how *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* are transmitted at the household level.

Antimicrobial resistance is an emerging problem worldwide. Worryingly, this limits accessible treatment options for humans.

If we find that animals present a risk for humans for transmission of *E. coli*, non-typhoidal *Salmonella* and antimicrobial resistance determinants, we will be able to provide advice and help for the community to limit the number of humans developing the disease, particularly with antimicrobial resistant strains, whilst at the same time maintaining animal health.

We would like to investigate the prevalence of several other diseases which pass between animals and humans in animals in Malawi. At the same time as sampling faeces, a small blood sample will be taken livestock (cattle, sheep, goats, pigs), domestic animals (dogs and cats) and rodents. Tests will be undertaken on this blood to ascertain whether animals in Malawi are exposed to these diseases. We would also like to examine faecal samples collected from the animals for the presence of worms and parasite eggs, which will indicate how the extent of the parasite burden affecting the animals.

WHY AM I BEING ASKED TO TAKE PART?

You are being asked to take part as your household is located within the study area of the Chikwawa Valley. Your household has been chosen at random from households in the District, using computer generated software.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO HUMANS AND ANIMALS INVOLVED?

It is likely that two visits will be made to the household over a one week period. Subsequent visits to the household will be made one month and six months after the first visits to repeat the sampling. Initially the project will be discussed with the head of the household and permission will be gained for sampling household members and animals. Consent will be gained from individual household members confirming that they are happy to participate in this project. Adults (either parents or guardians), will provide informed consent for children aged less than 18 years old, and children aged 8-18 years will offer assent that they are happy to participate in the project.

WHAT WILL HAPPEN TO MY SAMPLES?

Faecal and blood samples taken will be transported to the Liverpool-Malawi Wellcome Trust Laboratories, Queen Elizabeth Hospital, Blantyre where laboratory processing will be undertaken. Bacteria grown from samples, or the DNA from those bacteria, will be transported to the UK or Kenya for whole genome

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sequencing. Separated animal blood samples may be taken to the UK or Kenya for processing, should the appropriate tests not be available in Malawi. No human samples will leave Malawi.

WHAT INFORMATION WILL I BE ASKED TO PROVIDE?

In order to assist our understanding of the results gained from this project, before sampling we will ask you to provide the following information, if known, about your household:

1. Details of household members
2. Animal ownership
3. Recent illness of humans and animals
4. Antibiotic usage within a household (humans and animals)
5. Wildlife around the household
6. Sanitation within the household

This is to provide us with useful information when analyzing the results of the study.

WHAT IMPACT WILL THE STUDY HAVE ON ME?

RISKS

No risks will be present to household members or animals.

BENEFITS

This study will enable us to gain knowledge of the transmission route of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* within a household.

This study will determine whether antimicrobial resistance is affecting strains of *E. coli* and non-typhoidal *Salmonella* carried by members of the household.

This study will discover whether animals within the household have been exposed to various zoonotic pathogens or have a burden of parasites at the time of sampling.

The study will remunerate each household 8000 Malawi Kwacha per visit at each time point.

WHO WILL HAVE ACCESS TO THE INFORMATION YOU COLLECT ABOUT ME?

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Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome
Clinical Research Programme

Information collected during the study will be confidential and will only be able to be accessed by Dr Catherine Wilson. All samples will be logged and anonymized prior to entry to the study database. Should any significant results be found, with your permission, this information will be published in the relevant scientific literature to extend knowledge of diversity and transmission of *E. coli* and *Salmonella* at a household level in order to help inform the best way to limit disease spread.

WILL I FIND OUT ABOUT THE STUDY RESULTS?

Once the data from the study has been analysed, we will report the results to the Malawi Veterinary Authorities. Should there be any results of concern directly affecting your household, we will inform you of this and offer advice as to the appropriate Health and Safety considerations that should be made.

WHAT HAPPENS IF I DON'T WANT TO TAKE PART?

Although your help with this project will be greatly appreciated, there is no consequence if you decline to take part. We will not visit your household again for matters relating to this project. Thank you very much for reading this information sheet.

WHO CAN I GO TO FOR MORE INFORMATION ABOUT THIS?

Physical address and contact details of PI:

Catherine Wilson

Address: Malawi-Liverpool-Wellcome Trust Centre, Queen's Hospital, Blantyre, Malawi,

Email: c.n.wilson@liverpool.ac.uk

Physical address and contact details of Ethics Committee:

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